

ENHANCING GRADE 11 STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND MOTIVATION IN PHYSICAL SCIENCE USING CONTEXTUALIZED LEARNING WORKSHEET EMPHASIZING ENSCIEMA SKILLS

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Enhancing Grade 11 Students' Academic Performance and Motivation in Physical Science Using Contextualized Learning Worksheet Emphasizing ENSCIEMA Skills

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Abstract

This action research examined the effectiveness of utilizing the contextualized learning worksheet emphasizing the ENSCIEMA skills in improving their academic performance and motivation level in learning science concepts. The participants of the study were the grade 11 senior high school students who were officially enrolled in the School Year 2023-2024 at Silae National High School. The students were heterogeneous in composition. Pre-experimental research design was used in the study using non-probability sampling specifically total population sampling. The instruments used in the study were composed of the researchers made 30 test item multiple choice (pre-test and post-test) and adopted a survey questionnaire from Glynn & Koballa, 2006 for the assessment of motivation level of students. Descriptive statistics were used in the study using the mean and standard deviation (sd) in analyzing the data obtained from the results of the study in assessing the academic performance and motivation level of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of contextualized learning worksheet emphasizing the ENSCIEMA Skills and to identify the significant difference on the academic performance and motivation level of the students, paired t-test was used. The teacher conducted pre-test before the delivery of the lesson and post-test after the entire lesson were delivered. The academic performance test was based on the selected topics in the fourth quarter indicated on the MELCs set by the Department of Education and were evaluated by the schools' experts. Based on the results of the study, the academic performance as well the motivation level of the grade 11 senior high school students had a significant difference before and after the application of the intervention.

Keywords: *academic performance, motivation, contextualized, worksheets*

Introduction

In the context of teaching and learning process, it is very important for educators to innovate and think of new pedagogies for the betterment of learners. Hence, teachers keep on finding ways and means in alleviating the learning gaps of learners that needs to be addressed immediately. It has been observed that students nowadays got low scores in science and had difficulty also in developing the basic skills. They are not exerting much effort in thinking critically during class discussion and in terms of their communication and writing skills, they cannot totally express their ideas. With this, teachers are expected to be able to associate the learning material with the real-world situations of students in order to encourage them to make a connection between their knowledge and application in their daily lives. With that, the researchers came up with a contextualized learning worksheets for the students emphasizing the skills in core subjects English, Science and Mathematics in addressing the need to improve their literacy, numeracy and scientific skills in one setting.

The Silae National High School is located at Purok-3 Barangay Silae, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon with mountainous and rolling terrains lying in the Eastern part of Malaybalay City. It is bounded with its neighboring barangay of Mapulo, Malaybalay City Bukidnon and Iba, Cabanglasan, Bukidnon. As teachers assigned in rural areas, we encounter several challenges like lack of learning resources and availability of learning materials to be used in the teaching and learning process. With the current situation of the school, it is with the aim of this study to enhance and improve and the academic performance as well as the motivation level of the students highlighting the skills of the core subjects using contextualized learning worksheet in teaching physical science. In past years, students had trouble understanding the concepts taught in their science classes. Teachers require the latest innovations and the best methods for inspiring students to become actively involved in learning the subject.

Teachers find out that the learning activities of the module content is too complex and standard for the students to relate on a personal level. To address this problem, a contextualized learning activity sheets for science was made and utilized by the teachers. Localized and contextualized materials should be reproduced and immediately distributed, upon the implementation of the K to 12 curricula (Gianan, 2016). Educators in any field should try to apply or integrate localization and contextualization of learning materials in teaching any subject because it shows a positive effect on the performance of the learners and it is an effective means of imparting lifelong learning outcomes (Ballesteros, 2015).

Based on the result of the Basic Education Learning Assessment (BELA) of Grade 10 junior high school students conducted last school year 2021-2022, it shows that the Silae National High School got low mean percentage score in science compared to other schools of the Division of Malaybalay City which is only 33.6. Furthermore, there is a need for us to develop new learning material in developing the full potential of our students. According to Aguinaldo & Domingo, (2021), resources for education are crucial to the teaching and learning process. It also serves as a useful manual for how instruction is delivered in the classroom, which can improve students' academic achievement and general interest in the session. It is believed that the use of instructional resources is required to promote students' learning who have a variety of learning styles. In addition, with the study of Bello et. al. (2023), the K-12 curriculum's

implementation resulted in several reforms to the Philippine educational system, enhancing our students' overall and international competitiveness in scientific education nationwide. It is stated that "the curriculum shall use the spiral progression approach to ensure mastery of knowledge and skills after each level" in Philippine Republic Act 10533, also known as "The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013." This is the same as in the executing policy, which states that "the curriculum shall be contextualized and global and shall be flexible enough to enable and allow schools to be localized and indigenous and enhance the quality of education.

One of the themes enclosed in Department of Education (DepEd) Memorandum No. 39, series of 2016 known as the Adoption of the basic Education Research Agenda is the Teaching and Learning. DepEd seeks to ensure that learning outcomes are achieved by capitalizing on the competencies of teachers and potentials of all types of learners as the national institution mandated to provide quality basic education to all Filipinos. According to this Republic Act 10533, the curriculum must be learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally appropriate, relevant, responsive, contextualized, and global, but it must also be flexible enough to allow schools to localize, indigenize, and improve it in accordance with their unique educational and social contexts (Ligsanan, 2017).

According to Quisumbing (2017), it is remarkable for the teacher to develop instructional material to guide students in the academic performance. With the presence of this instructional material, the learning process can be fun because of the healthy exchange of information from the student and teacher. With the help of using contextual teaching and learning pedagogy, modern methods to science teachings such as inquiry, problem and project-based, cooperative learning, and authentic assessment can be employed such that the educational system in the country is upgrading learners to be globally competitive in pursuit of quality education and scientific literacy.

In the context of dealing with students, motivation also plays an important role in the teaching and learning process. Thus, it is one of the important components to cognition. It plays an important role in their conceptual change processes, critical thinking, learning strategies and achievement. Students are engaged when they feel included in the school and feel an emotional bond with the school, its teachers and their peers (Mai et. Al, 2023). More specifically, educators would improve their course materials to encourage students to participate actively in class (Suprapti et al., 2018).

Motivation encourages or persuades someone to do something because they have a burning urge to do so. Certainly, motivation is considered to be a significant factor in academic success since it energizes and drives behavior toward achievement (Steinmayr, 2019). Internal factors and external factors affect the performance of the students. Some become unmotivated, which leads to poor academic performance. They are more likely to have difficulties in comprehending lessons or have low critical thinking and difficulties in solving problems and having a hard time focusing on studying, given that science is filled with concepts, theories, and mathematics (Relianisa, 2020). Meanwhile, Chuter (2020), asserts that motivated students appear to have good and exemplary academic performance. They enjoy the challenge of thinking behind the lines, can think outside the box, and appear more intelligent. Notably, Science learning motivation is thought to be one of the most important factors in fostering a lifetime interest in science and increasing students' scientific literacy.

With this study, the teachers are hoping for the best result of students in learning science concepts and in acquiring necessary competencies. In line with that, the educational system is slowly upgrading the curriculum in the form of MATATAG Curriculum which aims to address the educational challenges that seeks to prioritize the mastery of literacy and numeracy skills among learners as well as aiming to reduce the number of competencies and to focus more on the development of foundational skills; literacy, numeracy, and socio-emotional skills of learners. The teachers were fully aware that this is not an easy task but still, they will do their best to provide quality education to learners so that they will be able to become an effective, competitive and functional individual in our society.

Innovation, Intervention, and Strategy

Contextualized curriculum helps students learn language skills by teaching the skills using the authentic contexts in which students must use those skills in the real world. Contextualizing curriculum is effective both for community-based and workplace classes. It helps teachers and students comprehend concepts by relating and presenting a lesson in the context of the prevailing local environment, culture, and resources. Hence, lessons are becoming more real-life, customized, and appropriate.

The researchers utilized the Contextualized Learning Worksheet emphasizing development in English, Science, and Mathematics skills of the students in teaching the Physical Science concepts that aims to enhance their academic performance and motivation level. This innovation has new features when compared to the usual learning worksheets because it is designed with contextualization and augmentation of the learning gap in the core subjects; English, Science and Mathematics. In this study, the following are the coverage lessons in the conduct of the study; Aristotelian vs. Galilean views of motion, mass, momentum and energy conservation, propagation of light, and the photon concept. The corresponding learning competencies indicated in the fourth quarter of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) for the three weeks of the implementation of the study were compare and contrast the Aristotelian and Galilean conceptions of vertical motion, horizontal motion and projectile motion, explain how Galileo inferred that objects in vacuum fall with uniform acceleration, and that force is not necessary to sustain horizontal motion, explain the subtle distinction between Newton's 1st Law of Motion (or Law of Inertia) and Galileo's assertion that force is not necessary to sustain horizontal motion, describe how the propagation of light, reflection, and refraction are explained by the wave model and the particle model of light, explain how the photon concept and the fact the energy of a photon is directly proportional to its frequency can be used to explain why red light is used in

photographic dark rooms, why we get easily sunburned in ultraviolet light but not in visible light and how we see colors, cite experimental evidence that electrons can behave like waves and differentiate dispersion, scattering, interference, and diffraction.

All of these concepts were aided with contextualized learning worksheets emphasizing the ENSCIEMA wherein the students were given time to answer activities and learn actively with a deeper understanding about the concepts using the worksheet. This innovation was crafted by the researchers that undergoes series of validation by the experts in the school before the utilization of the students. The contextualized learning worksheet can be printed that were distributed individually or non-printed via Bluetooth or link in the group chats in the messenger of the students during the conduct of the study. The learning worksheet has the following features: cover page, table of contents, overview of the lesson, learning competencies, enabling objectives, heading and the series of activities with instructions to be facilitated by the teachers, evaluation and references. The cover page contains the major information of the subject and the authors; the table of contents the list of lesson included and the activities to be performed by the students with its corresponding page number; the overview of the lesson will contain a brief information about the concepts of the lesson that was specific, clear and complete so that the learners can fully understand the lesson; the learning competencies and enabling objectives were based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) with specific code specified for that lesson; the heading consisted of the learner's name, grade and section and the date and for the practice exercises, it was composed of drills, puzzles, and other activities that were adopted or developed localized and contextualized by the teacher. The evaluation part was consisted of 10-15 item multiple choice test. References was added to serve as guide for students to for additional reading and source of information. The teacher then checked the outputs of the students and gave feedbacks. Compared to the usual worksheets, this innovation was unique because it makes use of activities that were contextualized and emphasizing the development of core subjects namely; English, science and mathematics.

All the lessons and needed materials developed by the researchers were checked and evaluated by the School Head, LRMSD Coordinator, expert in English for language and grammar used and science subject for the content. The evaluators were given checklist and set of criteria for the rating of instructional materials. The following criteria examined by the experts were the content, accuracy, clarity and appropriateness of the material. Suggestions and comments were considered for the final revision of the material.

In the implementation of the study, the researchers will follow the ADDIE Model (Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate). ADDIE model is one of the most common models used in the instructional design field a guide to producing an effective design. ADDIE helps identify the learning need in a structured way and ensures all learning activities serve that goal, which offers an integrated approach to learning. This model is an approach that helps instructional designers, any content's developer, or even teachers to create an efficient, effective teaching design by applying the processes of the ADDIE model on any instructional product (Aldoobie, 2015)

The first one is Analyze; the teacher identifies the background and needs of the learners in learning the science concept, the goals, and the teachers connect new perceptions with something familiar for students that helps students to linked their knowledge with new information thus, encouraging the students to relate daily events with the lessons that they learned. The second one is Design; after identifying the learning goals and the needs of the students, the teacher developed the specific learning objectives in which the teacher explicitly gave details on the expectation as to what to learn in the subject. The teacher identifies objectives of the lesson that includes the core competencies of the students, the length of the lesson that last for three weeks using the face-to-face sessions with the contextualized printed learning worksheets developed by the researchers. The third one is Develop; the teacher developed learning objectives, key content, and estimated time for each session. develop detailed content, learning activities, and served as the facilitator of instructions, review content to ensure logical flow, clarity of instructions, consistency of content, and comprehensiveness in meeting learning objectives. The teacher facilitated the learning process in which the students learned the context of exploration and experiences. They learn faster when they were able to use equipment and materials by themselves and helped them to practice actions that are straight connected to real-life work.

The fourth one is Implement; In here, the teacher puts the lesson into practice. The students applied the concept when they can apply their real-world experiences to their problem-solving activities. Teachers can motivate students by making problems realistic and relevant to students' life. And the last one is Evaluate, the teacher evaluated the implementation process and the learning outcome of the students. In this stage the teacher helped students to take what they have learned and apply it to new situations and contexts.

This was also anchored from two educational learning theories which are the constructivist and cognitive learning theory. Constructivist teaching and learning theory advocates a participatory approach in which students actively participate in the learning process. It involves an active learning process wherein information may be imposed, but understanding cannot be, for it must come from within. It requires a teacher to act as a facilitator whose main function is to help students become active participants in their learning and make meaningful connections between prior knowledge, new knowledge, and the processes involved in learning. Constructivist teachers encourage students to constantly assess how the activity is helping them gain understanding. This gives them ever-broadening tools to keep learning. With a well- planned classroom environment, the students learn how to learn. (Gordon, 2009).

In relation to cognition, learning involves the internal and external domains. Learning therefore involves processing of information as a way of interaction between these two domains. Cognitivism, constructivism and related theories such as the cognitive theory of multimedia learning address the input of information from the external world into the cognitive structures, the cognitive processing of this information, and the externalization of information from the mind to the world/environment. (Mnguni, 2014).

Action Research Questions

This action research examined the effectiveness of utilizing Contextualized Learning Worksheet emphasizing the ENSCIEMA Skills in improving their Academic Performance and Motivation level in Physical Science among Grade 11 Senior High School students at Silae National High School for the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the academic performance of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of Contextualized Learning Worksheet emphasizing ENSCIEMA Skills?
2. What is the motivation level of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of Contextualized Learning Worksheet emphasizing ENSCIEMA Skills?
3. Is there a significant difference on the academic performance of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of Contextualized Learning Worksheet emphasizing ENSCIEMA Skills?
4. Is there a significant difference on the motivation level of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of Contextualized Learning Worksheet emphasizing ENSCIEMA Skills?

Methodology

Participants

The study was conducted at Silae National High School located at Silae, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. The participants of the study were the Grade 11 curriculum who were officially enrolled in the School Year 2023-2024. The students were heterogeneous in composition and all of them were chosen as the participants of the study.

Table 1. *Number of Participants*

	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Grade 11 Curriculum	21	20	41

Reliability test was conducted in the conduct of the study wherein Fifty (50) test items were crafted by the researchers. Pilot testing was then employed to Grade 12 students. After the pilot testing, reliability analysis test was used using Cronbach Alpha model to determine the level of internal consistency of the test questions and since the resulting Cronbach Alpha was .894 which means that the test questions were good and it was then selected down to thirty (30) test items. Pre-experimental research design was used using non-probability sampling specifically total population sampling. Before the implementation of the intervention, the teacher conducted pre-test. Right after the pre-test, implementation of the intervention was then conducted in the class sessions with the desired target lessons. After the implementation, Post-test were then given to the students. The result of the scores of the students based from the pre-test and post-test was compared and treated as the independent variable of the study.

Procedure

In this study, the teacher conducted pre-test before the delivery of the lessons and administered post-test after the entire lesson were delivered. The independent variable in the study was the used of contextualized learning worksheets emphasizing ENSCIEMA skills of the students and the dependent variables were the academic performance and motivation level of the students in physical science.

Instrumentation of the Study

The instruments used in the study were the researcher's made 30 test item multiple choice academic performance test (pre-test and post-test) and adopted a survey questionnaire in measuring the motivation level of the Grade 11 senior high school students from Glynn & Koballa, 2006. The academic performance test was based on the selected topics in the fourth quarter indicated on the MELCs set by the Department of Education. This subject covers the comparison and contrast of the Aristotelian and Galilean conceptions of vertical motion, horizontal motion and projectile motion, explain how Galileo inferred that objects in vacuum fall with uniform acceleration, and that force is not necessary to sustain horizontal motion, explain the subtle distinction between Newton's 1st Law of Motion (or Law of Inertia) and Galileo's assertion that force is not necessary to sustain horizontal motion, describe how the propagation of light, reflection, and refraction are explained by the wave model and the particle model of light, explain how the photon concept and the fact the energy of a photon is directly proportional to its frequency can be used to explain why red light is used in photographic dark rooms, why we get easily sunburned in ultraviolet light but not in visible light and how we see colors, cite experimental evidence that electrons can behave like waves and differentiate dispersion, scattering, interference, and diffraction. The construction of the test item was guided with Table of Specifications (TOS) with the following cognitive process and dimension: remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating and creating.

The academic performance test was validated by the School Head and experts in science at Silae National High School for the checking of content of the subject area and English teacher for the language and grammar used. The bases for the validation were the content, content accuracy, clarity and appropriateness. The comments gathered were considered by the researchers for the final revision of the material. To assess the motivation of the students, the researcher adopted with modification a motivational survey questionnaire from Glynn & Koballa, 2006 with the Cronbach alpha value of 0.91 to measure the effectiveness of utilizing contextualized learning worksheet to the Grade 11 senior high school students in Silae National High School. This tool will be administered to all the

participants in the study and will be subjected for statistical analysis.

Implementation of the Study

In the conduct of the study, it undergoes four stages namely; the planning stage, development stage, validation stage and implementation stage. For the planning stage, the researchers determined the purpose of making the learning worksheet, the topics to be included, sources, and as well as the process of identifying characteristics and needs of the students. In the development stage, the researchers made and designed researchers made contextualized learning worksheets emphasizing the ENSCIEMA Skills as well as the assessment tool needed. In the academic assessment for pre-test and post-test, the researcher crafted 50 multiple choice test that undergoes pilot testing to test the consistency of the test questions and were then selected down to 30 items that covers all the topics included.

For the assessment in the motivation level of the students, an adopted with modification motivational survey questionnaire from Glynn & Koballa, 2006 with the Cronbach alpha value of 0.91 which is considered as excellent. In the validation stage, the experts checked and evaluated the content, language, the suitability of learning objectives with materials, the face validity that includes the suitability of choosing the type of font, and appearance that will be performed by the School Head, Academic Head, English teachers and the LRMS In-charge. The evaluators were given checklist and set of criteria for the rating of instructional materials that was used. The following criteria examined were the content, accuracy, clarity and appropriateness of the material. Suggestions and comments were considered for the final revision of the material.

And lastly will be on the Implementation stage, the researchers conducted the pre-test before the utilization of the crafted contextualized learning worksheet in the teaching and learning process. Right after the pre-test, implementation of the intervention was done during the class session in which the contextualized learning worksheets were printed to be used by the students. After the implementation, the researcher conducted post-test. Descriptive statistics were used in the study using the mean and standard deviation (sd) in analyzing the data obtained from the results of the study in assessing the academic performance and motivation level of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of contextualized learning worksheet emphasizing the ENSCIEMA Skills and to identify the significant difference on the academic performance and motivation level of the students, paired t-test was used.

Data Analysis

The researchers asked permission from the offices of the School Head and the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Malaybalay City before the conduct of the study. Confidentiality of the research data were also properly secured as well as their consent. In order for participants to grasp the significant information and make a fully informed, deliberate, and freely given decision about whether or not to do so without the use of any pressure or coercion, the researcher will supply sufficient information and assurances regarding participating. In the conduct of the study, offensive, discriminatory, or other undesirable wording were avoided.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers asked permission from the offices of the School Head and the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Malaybalay City before the conduct of the study. Confidentiality of the research data were also properly secured as well as their consent. In order for participants to grasp the significant information and make a fully informed, deliberate, and freely given decision about whether or not to do so without the use of any pressure or coercion, the researcher will supply sufficient information and assurances regarding participating. In the conduct of the study, offensive, discriminatory, or other undesirable wording were avoided.

Results and Discussion

The main purpose of the study was to examine the effectiveness of the utilization of the contextualized learning worksheet emphasizing the ENSCIEMA skills of Grade 11 senior high school students in improving their academic performance and motivation level in learning physical science concepts. Comparison of the statistical results in the pre-test and post-test of the academic performance of the students was obtained and the outcome of the assessment in the motivation level of the students was also analyzed.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics, Frequency and Percentage of the scores in Academic Performance of students

Level of Proficiency	Range of Scores	Achievement Range	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	28-30	90% above	0	0	9	21.95
Very Satisfactory	25-27	85%-89%	0	0	29	70.73
Satisfactory	22-24	80%-84%	0	0	2	4.88
Fairly Satisfactory	19-21	75%-79%	7	17.07	1	2.44
Did Not Meet Expectations	0-18	74% below	34	82.93	0	0
Mean			13.4390		26.3171	
Standard Deviation			3.60589		1.52380	
Achievement Level			Did Not Meet Expectations		Very Satisfactory	

The mean score of the students in the pre-test was only 13 which signifies that the achievement level of the students before the intervention was “did not meet expectation” and right after the intervention was 26 which means that the students achievement level was very satisfactory which was way higher when compared to the pre-test score. As presented in the table, 83% of the students got scores below 18 and on the post-test scores, none of them got below 18 and 71% of the students got the score from a range of 25-27 that was very satisfactory which means that there was a significant increase in the scores of the students. When it comes to the standard deviation of the scores in pre-test of the students, it was quite distributed that indicates that the scores are spread out when compared to the standard deviation of the scores in the post-test of the students.

This implies that the scores of the students in the pre-test means that they had a struggle with knowledge, skills and understanding and have not acquired or developed to aid understanding. Moreover, it also suggests that students need to learn more about the concept by engaging them in a more holistic approach by providing them supplemental instruction in the teaching and learning process in augmenting the learning gaps of the students. In the classroom setting, we observed that students nowadays are not exerting much effort in thinking beyond the box. They only want to have an easy way task or simply depending on the sources without having a simple comprehension of the task given. Hence, the focus of education needs to be shifted from placing content in students’ knowledge building. If the focus of studying could be turned from filling one’s mind to producing performance-based products, students wouldn’t need to concentrate on rote memorization. In classroom instruction there is a need of integration of formal, theoretical, practical and self-regulative knowledge. According to Fernando & Marikar (2017), the constructivist approach emphasizes that the active construction of knowledge by the learner is socially and culturally rooted.

On the other hand, the scores in the post-test signifies that the students gained higher scores and majority of them increases and were in achievement level “very satisfactory” which confirms that the learners at this level developed the fundamental core understanding in terms of knowledge, skills and understanding, and transfer them automatically through authentic performance task. This simply implies that the students find the contextualized learning worksheets emphasizing the ENSCIEMA skills very helpful and effective in the teaching and learning process. Since English, Science, and Mathematics subjects were considered as the core subjects, then it is a must for us, educators, to strengthen the skills for basic numeracy and literacy of the students especially that they need to acquire these basic skills in order to have a holistic learning in the subject.

The findings from the table above revealed that using contextualized learning worksheets allows the students to relate science concepts to real-life facts, improving their understanding of the subject. Consequently, the results also imply that contextualization can aid the students in connecting concepts and experiences they acquired in learning and applying them to unusual and complex issues, discipline, and various settings. Subsequently, the developed material assists the students in making connections with new ideas and experiences that can help with activities that need more information and expertise to better cope with everyday tasks.

According to Fauziah, A.M & Nurita, T. (2019), contextualized learning worksheets can help students understand the subject matter more easily. In addition, Constructivism also proposes that learners create knowledge as they attempt to understand their experiences. Aldridge and Goldman (2007) advocated also that the crucial role of the school system in student success is that school systems must be informed of current research and must be provided with opportunities to explore and adopt strategies that have the greatest potential of enhancing student development and achievement. In which Rababah (2021) presumes that the Learners aren't hollow minds waiting to be filled with knowledge. Learners, on the other hand, actively seek to create meaning. Learners also make decisions about what they want to learn and how they want to learn it.

According to Dumajog (2020), using localized examples, exercises, and illustrations when teaching science concepts can improve student success in science. This teaching strategy involves incorporating local data into the educational material, which can make it more relatable and engaging for students. Curriculum experts recommend using authentic and native examples and exercises to make this teaching approach effective.

Table 3. *Motivation of Grade 11 Senior High School Students*

	<i>Before</i>			<i>After</i>		
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Overall Motivation Level	3.35	.15	Moderately Motivated	4.34	.16	Very High Motivated

Based from the results presented in table 3, before the intervention, the students got a mean score of 3.35 which was interpreted as moderately motivated and right after the intervention, the students got a mean score of 4.34 which means that they are very highly motivated. It implies that the intervention contributed to the increase of motivation level of students in the teaching and learning process. As an educator, we are very glad that the students were at least exerting effort in doing the activities and were interested to learn more about the science concepts. Indeed, it was transformational and informational because the students make use of their higher order thinking skills in answering the questions and task given with the best of their ability especially in improving their scientific skills, their vocabulary skills, problem solving skills and numeracy skills.

The contextualized learning worksheet utilized by the students provides activities that allow them to explore new ideas and learning

concepts on their own, leading to a more fruitful learning outcome. Generally, the result suggests that incorporating contextualized activity tools as a learning resource helps learners feel motivated to learn the topic on their abilities, understand the lesson, appreciate its meaning and usefulness, and connect and apply it in everyday activities.

According to Astrodjojo (2018), a teacher should be able to apply various techniques that can change the way students learn from passive into active so that the students will be much more interested and familiar with what is being taught by the teacher. The low activity students can still be seen from the lack of courage of the students asking questions, answering questions from teachers, expressed his opinion and worked on the matter of exercise in front of the class. Learning involves students actively can help develop their critical thinking ability.

Table 4. Paired *t*-Test value of Means of Academic Performance of students

Pair	Pretest - Posttest	Paired Differences				<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	Sig. (2- tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			
					Lower Upper			
1	- 12.878	- 3.835	.599	-14.089 -11.667	- 21.500	40	.000	

In table 4, it reveals the paired *t*-test value of means of academic performance of students wherein it shows that there was a significant difference on the academic performance of students in physical science before and after the intervention. The mean difference of pre-test and post-test was -12.878 which means that there was an increase of the scores of the students. Since the *p* value was less than 0.001 which was lesser than the level of significance, the difference was statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected thus accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that there was a significant difference on the academic performance of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of contextualized learning worksheet emphasizing the ENSCIEMA skills of students. The researchers were also 95% confident that the actual mean difference between the pre-test and post-test was between -14.089 and -11.667 and that means that were very confident that the score before the intervention was always less than after the intervention.

It also signifies that the values of the scores of the students had a significant difference statistically. However, the standard deviation indicated that the scores were quite distributed because some of them attained the outstanding level and majority of them got the very satisfactory while only few falls under the satisfactory and fairly satisfactory level. In addition, learning must not only be incorporated in a curriculum but also the tasks, learning situations and interaction with the social environment of the learner. The process of contextualization and de-contextualization is also important for abstraction and generalization of knowledge.

The education sector had significant setbacks during the Covid-19 pandemic. Classes were suddenly halted indefinitely, and underprivileged students encountered challenges such as inequitable access to technology and internet resources. This incident served as a further obstacle for the country, which was already struggling to enhance the quality of fundamental education before the pandemic (Bisnar, 2022). Teachers face the greatest challenge in finding ways to succeed with various types of learners despite the educational crisis that we are currently experiencing. The role of teachers is crucial when it comes to assisting students' needs, especially in overcoming difficulties in learning science. According to Simon (2008), relevant changes in the curriculum need to offer explicit instruction; thus, pedagogy plays an important role in achieving curriculum goals (Montilla et al., 2023).

Furthermore, scientific learners encounter numerous obstacles during the learning process, leading to subpar academic performance. Some individuals encounter challenges in understanding educational content, determining problem-solving strategies, and articulating scientific concepts. Education in the mentioned sector is dynamic, intricate, and continuous. Science education activities enhance students' cognitive abilities, enabling them to think logically, methodically, objectively, and comprehensively.

Additionally, these activities foster an objective and receptive mindset when addressing various matters. Moreover, possessing critical thinking abilities enables students to employ advanced and thought-provoking cognitive processes to engage in creative and analytical thinking. The combination of imaginative and critical thinking has the potential to foster national growth and address societal requirements (Yuanita et al., 2018).

Contextualization is an educational approach that establishes connections between concepts and subjects in the curriculum. The science curriculum involves incorporating the desired skills and knowledge into a practical instructional environment to enhance the relevance and effectiveness of the teaching and learning experience for students. Orpwood et al. (2010) state that contextualization can involve several elements, such as interdisciplinary learning, incorporating students' informal knowledge from outside of school, teachers working together to highlight real-world examples, and promoting student collaboration and active learning.

According to Kaphur (2019), one of the core elements that will promote student learning and help achieve academic goals and objectives is the development of teaching-learning materials in educational institutions. Teachers must focus on bringing about improvements in teaching and learning resources. Educators must ensure that they are effective in helping students achieve their learning objectives after they have been implemented.

Table 5. *t*-Test value of Means of the Level of Motivation of Grade 11 Senior High School Students

Pair	Pretest - Posttest	Paired Differences				<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
1		-.989	.239	.044	Lower -1.078	Upper -.899	-	29	.000
							22.614		

Based from the result presented in table 5 reveals that the *p* value was less than 0.001 which was lesser than the level of significance, the difference was statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted stating that there was a significant difference on the motivation level of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of intervention. The mean difference of pre-test and post-test was -.989 which means that there was an increase of the mean score of the motivation level of students. The researchers were also 95% confident that the actual mean difference between before and after the motivation level of students was between -1.078 and -.899 and that means that were very confident that the score before the intervention was always less than after the intervention.

The result implies that when contextualization is applied within the lesson context, students can easily grasp the lessons. Moreover, the result demonstrates that when students are given profound targets for the lesson, they are more engaged and inspired to learn the new concepts being studied. They also show eagerness to meet the expected outcome set by the teacher. Furthermore, students' eagerness to discover new things positively impacts the learning process, boosts their satisfaction, and can influence information analysis, resulting in improved performance. It also indicates that the hands-on activities successfully stimulated learners to independently engage in learning, improving their comprehension of the lesson's context and fostering advanced cognitive abilities.

According to Williams (2011), motivation is crucial for effective learning. It is argued that students with better motivation usually perform better in school grades. He also stresses that motivation is probably the most important factor that educators can target in order to improve learning. Purportedly, academic performance in science is equated to students' motivation and interests in the academic pursuits that they do. Presenting the lesson using a contextual approach motivates students, as it challenges them to apply scientific reasoning to different contexts and actively engages them in higher-order thinking

As supported by Steinmayr, 2019, motivation is considered to be a significant factor in academic success since it energizes and drives behavior toward achievement. Internal factors and external factors affect the performance of the students. Some become unmotivated, which leads to poor academic performance. They are more likely to have difficulties in comprehending lessons or have low critical thinking and difficulties in solving problems and having a hard time focusing on studying, given that science is filled with concepts, theories, and mathematics (Relianisa, 2020). Meanwhile, Chuter (2020), asserts that motivated students appear to have good and exemplary academic performance. They enjoy the challenge of thinking behind the lines, can think outside the box, and appear more intelligent. Notably, Science learning motivation is thought to be one of the most important factors in fostering a lifetime interest in science and increasing students' scientific literacy.

Contextualized curriculum helps students learn language skills by teaching the skills using the authentic contexts in which students must use those skills in the real world. Contextualizing curriculum is effective both for community-based and workplace classes. It helps teachers and students comprehend concepts by relating and presenting a lesson in the context of the prevailing local environment, culture, and resources. Hence, lessons are becoming more real-life, customized, and appropriate.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: First, it was concluded that there was a significant increased on the academic performance of the students after the intervention since the student's achievement level was very satisfactory which was way higher when compared to the pre-test score which means that there was a significant increase in the scores of the students. This implies that the scores of the students in the pre-test means that they had a struggle with knowledge, skills and understanding and have not acquired or developed to aid understanding. On the other hand, the scores in the post-test signifies that the students gained higher scores and majority of them increases and were in achievement level "very satisfactory" which confirms that the learners at this level developed the fundamental core understanding in terms of knowledge, skills and understanding, and transfer them automatically through authentic performance task.

Second, it was also concluded that the motivation of students developed and improved and was interpreted as very highly motivated. It implies that the intervention contributed to the increase of motivation level of students in the teaching and learning process. The contextualized learning worksheet utilized by the students provides activities that allow them to explore new ideas and learning concepts on their own, leading to a more fruitful learning outcome. Generally, the result suggests that incorporating contextualized activity tools as a learning resource helps learners feel motivated to learn the topic on their abilities, understand the lesson, appreciate its meaning and usefulness, and connect and apply it in everyday activities.

Third, it was concluded that there was a significant difference on the academic performance of students in physical science before and

after the intervention. The mean difference was statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected thus accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that there was a significant difference on the academic performance of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of contextualized learning worksheet emphasizing the ENSCIEMA skills of students.

And lastly, the mean difference of the motivation level of students was statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted stating that there was a significant difference on the motivation level of grade 11 senior high school students before and after the use of intervention. The result implies that when contextualization is applied within the lesson context, students can easily grasp the lessons. Moreover, the result demonstrates that when students are given profound targets for the lesson, they are more engaged and inspired to learn the new concepts being studied. They also show eagerness to meet the expected outcome set by the teacher. Furthermore, students' eagerness to discover new things positively impacts the learning process, boosts their satisfaction, and can influence information analysis, resulting in improved performance. It also indicates that the hands-on activities successfully stimulated learners to independently engage in learning, improving their comprehension of the lesson's context and fostering advanced cognitive abilities. Therefore, it can be concluded that using contextualized learning worksheets can effectively increase the academic performance and motivation of students that can enhance student learning and engagement. Incorporating contextualized examples and exercises can make the material more relevant and meaningful for students, leading to a more enjoyable and effective learning experience.

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